

Leadership Proficiency of School Heads and Teachers’ Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao Del Sur

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Abstract. The study examined the influence of school heads’ leadership proficiency on teachers’ commitment to classroom organization. The researcher selected 190 elementary school teachers in the Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur as the survey respondents in this study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the leadership proficiency of school heads was rated as extensive, while teachers’ classroom organization commitment was rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between the leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers’ classroom organization commitment. Regression analysis proved that school heads’ leadership proficiency in curriculum and assessment and teacher development and support significantly influence the teachers’ commitment to the classroom organization. The department was recommended to allocate resources to support ongoing research and evaluation efforts to identify effective leadership practices that positively impact teacher commitment and classroom organization. It was further recommended that findings be used through publication in reputable research journals.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management
2. leadership proficiency of school heads
3. teachers’ classroom organization commitment

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1. Introduction

The leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers’ commitment to classroom organization are essential components of effective education. When school leaders provide strong direction, allocate resources wisely, and foster a culture of excellence, they create an environment where teachers’ commitment to classroom organization can thrive. School heads provide the vision and strategic direction for the school. Their leadership proficiency ensures that the school has a clear mission, goals, and a plan to achieve them. This vision guides all educational activities and decisions. Meanwhile, commitment to classroom organization allows teachers to maximize instructional time. Well-organized classrooms enable efficient transitions between

activities, leading to more effective teaching. Together, these factors contribute to a positive, engaging, and successful student learning experience. As highlighted by Glickman et al. (2014), proficient school heads can provide targeted support and resources to foster continuous teacher professional development. They can identify areas of improvement, offer relevant training opportunities, and facilitate reflective practices, ultimately enhancing teacher effectiveness. Likewise, supervisory competence allows school heads to guide teachers in adopting innovative and learner-focused instructional methods, catering to diverse learning needs and enhancing learner engagement. Also, the idea indicated that supervisory competence helps school heads guide teachers in effectively using digital tools to enhance instruction, communication, and student learning experiences. Previous literature indicated that the leadership proficiency of school heads plays a critical role in influencing teachers' classroom organization commitment. For instance, Porter et al. (2013) found that proficient school heads provide constructive feedback and recognition for teachers' efforts. The author emphasized that when teachers receive meaningful feedback and acknowledgment for their hard work, they feel valued and motivated to maintain their commitment to the classroom organization. Similarly, the study conducted by Harris and Jones (2017) showed that influential school leaders prioritize teachers' professional growth and provide opportunities for ongoing development. A supportive supervisory environment that encourages continuous learning fosters teachers' dedication to improving their skills and knowledge. As highlighted by Bolman and Deal (2014), teachers' commitment to classroom organization is of utmost importance in the teaching-learning processes for many reasons. It was pointed out that a dedicated teacher possesses the passion, commitment, and intrinsic motivation necessary to create a positive and impactful learning environment. According to Sabir et al. (2020), dedicated teachers are enthusiastic and committed to their profession, translating into engaging and dynamic classroom experiences. Their passion for teaching captivates students' interest and encourages active participation, increasing student engagement and learning motivation. Likewise, Condon and Clifford (2015) noted that dedicated teachers serve as role models for their students. Their dedication to continuous learning and growth inspires students to adopt a similar mindset, encouraging them to become lifelong learners and pursue excellence. However, several studies and reports have explored the impact of low teachers' classroom organization commitment on various aspects of the teaching-learning process. For instance, Maslach and Leiter (2016) reported that low dedication and high job dissatisfaction can contribute to teacher burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion and feelings of depersonalization. Also, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) reported that diminished dedication may result in a higher teacher turnover rate, as educators may seek alternative career paths or more supportive work environments. High teacher turnover can disrupt continuity in schools and negatively impact student learning. In addition, the report of Ladd and Sorensen (2018) indicated that diminished teacher dedication disproportionately affects schools in underserved areas, exacerbating educational inequalities. Most studies focus on school leaders' perceptions, and there is a limited understanding of how teachers perceive and experience the impact of leadership proficiency on their commitment to classroom organization. Research should incorporate teacher voices and perspectives to provide a more comprehensive understanding. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in the Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used a descriptive

correlational design to understand the teachers' classroom organization commitment as determined by the leadership proficiency of school heads, which is found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the influence of leadership proficiency of school heads on teachers' classroom organization commitment. Bryman and Bell (2015) described quantitative research as a research method that focuses on the objective measurement and analysis of numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach employs systematic and structured data collection techniques, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather numerical data that could be quantified and statistically analyzed. The findings from quantitative research aim to provide a deeper understanding of patterns, relationships, and trends within the data. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Gay, Mills, and Airasian (2019), is an approach that involves observing and measuring two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to describe the relationship or association between variables as they naturally occur. This approach focuses on understanding the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, often using statistical measures such as correlation coefficients. In a descriptive correlational study, researchers collect data on variables of interest and analyze them to identify patterns, trends, or associations. The goal was to gain a deeper understanding of how the variables relate to each other in a specific population or context. More so, this approach is particularly useful when exploring complex phenomena or when causality cannot be established due to ethical or practical limitations. Particularly, the study focused on determining which domains of leadership proficiency of school heads significantly influence the teachers' classroom organization commitment.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were elementary school teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. In this study, the 190 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling, according to Leedy and Ormrod (2018), is a probabilistic sampling technique used in research to select a representative sample from a population by dividing it into subgroups or strata based on certain characteristics. Within each stratum, a random sample is drawn, and these samples are combined to create the final representative sample for the study. This method ensures that each subgroup is adequately represented in the sample, allowing for more accurate generalizations and inferences to be made about the entire population. Moreover, the primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur, those who were not subjected to any administrative or criminal complaints, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the gender and socioeconomic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument concerned about the leadership proficiency of school heads which was conceptualized by Lunenburg and Ornstein (2012). The questionnaire consisted of four domains, namely: curriculum and assessment, teacher

development and support, instructional leadership, and resource management. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of leadership proficiency of school heads, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean Scores and Descriptive Levels for Leadership Proficiency of School Heads

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The leadership proficiency of school heads is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The leadership proficiency of school heads is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The leadership proficiency of school heads is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The leadership proficiency of school heads is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The leadership proficiency of school heads is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was about the teachers’ classroom organization commitment, which was intellectualized by Thomas and Johnson (2006) and divided into four domains, namely: Passion for teaching, commitment to student success, personal sacrifice, and innovation and creativity. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items

in each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ classroom organization commitment, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

The questionnaire was pilot-tested in a nearby school and obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value greater than 0.700, which ensured that the questionnaires had a high level of internal consistency. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average

cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments.

Range of Mean Scores and Descriptive Levels for Teachers' Commitment to Classroom Organization

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' commitment to classroom organization is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' classroom organization commitment is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' classroom organization commitment is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' classroom organization commitment is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' classroom organization commitment is never manifested.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school's division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The

researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the questionnaire administration, the researcher distributed the questionnaires following health protocols. The participants of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Data Analysis—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers' commitment to classroom organization in Kiblawan

South District, Davao del Sur. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between the leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers' classroom organi-

zation commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by *r*. This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression was applied to eval-

uate the significance of school head leadership proficiency on teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur; the significant relationship between leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur; and the significant influence of leadership proficiency of school heads on the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur.

The Leadership Proficiency of School Heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Table 1 shows the leadership proficiency of school heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. It shows that the overall mean leadership proficiency of school heads is 3.43, which is described as extensive. It means that the leadership proficiency of school heads is oftentimes observed. This means that these principals understand the significance of fostering a positive school climate. They prioritize creating an environment where collaboration,

respect, and trust thrive among staff members, students, and parents. A positive school climate not only enhances teacher job satisfaction but also contributes to student engagement and overall academic success. The result corroborates with Eng and Ramiah's (2017) idea that school heads who are competent in supervising exhibit a range of characteristics that enable them to lead, manage, and support their school community effectively. These characteristics create a positive and conducive learning environment, promote teacher development, and drive school improvement.

Table 1. Summary of Leadership Proficiency of School Heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Curriculum and Assessment	3.49	Extensive
Teacher Development and Support	3.62	Extensive
Instructional Leadership	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Resource Management	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

More so, the leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of teacher development and support acquired the highest mean score

of 3.62, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of instructional

leadership got the lowest mean score of 3.30 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. Bean and Lillenstein (2014) argue that school principals with strong supervisory skills play a crucial role in guiding and assisting teachers, cultivating a favorable school atmosphere, and promoting ongoing enhancement in student academic performance. Effective school leadership involves more than just administrative tasks; it requires the ability to provide meaningful guidance and support to teachers. Principals with supervisory competence are adept at offering constructive feedback, mentoring teachers, and facilitating professional development opportunities. By doing so, they empower educators to excel in their roles and contribute positively to student learning outcomes.

The Summary of Teachers’ Classroom Organization Commitment

As shown in Table 2, is the summary of teachers’ classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. As shown in the table, teachers’ classroom organi-

zation commitment obtained an overall mean score of 3.34 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers. The outcome indicates that teachers are effectively carrying out their duties, delivering a satisfactory educational experience, and sustaining stable morale. Nevertheless, they may not demonstrate extraordinary dedication or innovation in their teaching methods. Teachers who display exceptional enthusiasm and innovation are not content with the status quo; instead, they continually seek ways to improve their practice and make learning more meaningful and impactful for their students. This discovery aligns with the perspective presented by Bibiso (2017), which suggests that committed educators exhibit a profound sense of accountability towards the academic progress and welfare of their students. They exceed expectations in crafting a favorable and influential educational journey, investing their time, dedication, and emotional commitment to foster the advancement and flourishing of their students.

Table 2. Summary of Teachers’ Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Passion For Teaching	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Commitment to Student Success	3.38	Extensive
Personal Sacrifice	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Innovation and Creativity	3.42	Extensive
Overall	3.34	Moderately Extensive

Adding more, results in Table 2 show that teachers’ classroom organization commitment in terms of innovation and creativity acquired the highest mean score of 3.42, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. In contrast, teachers’ classroom organization commitment in terms of personal sacrifice acquired the lowest mean score of 3.24 described

as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested among teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. Dedicated teachers are driven by a passion for teaching and a genuine desire to positively impact their students’ lives. They take joy in helping students learn and grow academically, socially, and emotionally and derive fulfillment from the mean-

ingful connections they forge in the classroom. Mfaume and Bilinga (2017) highlighted that devoted educators possess a strong passion for their vocation and derive genuine satisfaction from interacting with students. They take joy in facilitating their students' academic, social, and emotional growth.

Relationship Between Leadership Proficiency of School Heads and Teachers' Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

The results of the analysis on the relationship between leadership proficiency of school heads and teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between the mentioned variables. Table 3 shows that the leadership proficiency of school heads has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' classroom organization commitment with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.554$, $p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of leadership proficiency of school heads changes, teachers' classroom organization commitment also changes significantly. Adding more, results on the table shows that leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of curriculum and assessment; teacher development and support; instructional leadership; and resource management have significant positive relationship

Influence of Leadership Proficiency of School Heads on the Teachers' Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

The significance on the influence of leadership proficiency of school heads on the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur was analyzed using linear regression analysis. The Ta-

with the teachers' dedication with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.411$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.526$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.229$, $p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.333$, $p < 0.05$), respectively. The findings underscore the crucial role of school leaders in providing clear guidance and direction to teachers within the educational setting. By setting forth explicit expectations and outlining measurable goals, competent administrators create a framework within which teachers can effectively plan and execute their instructional practices. This corroborates Louis' (2010) research, indicating that effective school administrators establish transparent expectations and objectives for teachers. When educators have a clear understanding of their responsibilities and specific targets to aim for, they are more inclined to demonstrate dedication towards accomplishing these objectives. Moreover, the result emphasized the importance of fair and transparent teacher evaluations in promoting educator dedication and professionalism. When educators perceive the evaluation process as equitable and growth-oriented, it fosters a culture of continuous improvement and supports their commitment to the teaching profession. Danielson and McGreal (2000) assert that effective supervisory competence encompasses conducting fair and transparent teacher evaluations. When educators perceive the evaluation process as impartial and geared towards professional growth, they are more inclined to demonstrate dedication to their profession.

ble 4 shows that when leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of curriculum and assessment; teacher development and support; instructional leadership; and resource management are considered as predictors of teachers' classroom organization commitment, the model is significant as evident on F-value of 27.837 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that leadership proficiency of school heads predicts the teachers' class-

Table 3. Relationship Between Leadership Proficiency of School Heads and Teachers' Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Curriculum and Assessment	0.411*	0.000	Reject H0
Teacher Development and Support	0.526*	0.000	Reject H0
Instructional Leadership	0.229*	0.001	Reject H0
Resource Management	0.333*	0.001	Reject H0
Overall Leadership Proficiency of School Heads	0.554*	0.000	Reject H0

**Significant @ p<0.05*

Legend: Perfect Correlation for r=1.00; Strong Correlation for 0.7<r<1.00; Moderate Correlation for 0.3<r<0.7; Weak Correlation for 0.3<r<0.00; No Correlation for r=0.00

room organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.351 indicates that leadership proficiency of school heads has contributed significantly in the variability of teachers' classroom organization commitment by 35.10 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 64.90 was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

Table 4. Influence of Leadership Proficiency of School Heads on the Teachers' Classroom Organization Commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Leadership Proficiency of School Heads	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decisions
Curriculum and Assessment	.161*	.231	.045	.000	Reject H0
Teacher Development and Support	.295*	.408	.047	.000	Reject H0
Instructional Leadership	.085	.108	.049	.082	Accept H0
Resource Management	.075	.098	.052	.111	Accept H0

R2 = 0.351

F-value = 27.837*

p-value = 0.000

**Significant @ p<0.05*

In addition, table shows that there are domains of leadership proficiency of school heads that significantly influence the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. This table also indicates that leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of curriculum and assessment; and teacher development and support are significant when considered as predictors of teachers' classroom organization commitment. This

means that the extent of teachers' classroom organization commitment increases by 0.161 and 0.295 for each unit increase in leadership proficiency of school heads. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domains of leadership proficiency of school heads that significantly influence the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. This denotes that when teachers receive meaningful feedback and recognition, it promotes a culture of continuous improvement and professional growth within the school community. This aligns with the assertion made by Porter and colleagues (2013)

that effective school administrators offer constructive feedback and appreciation to teachers for their endeavors. When educators are provided with insightful feedback and recognition for their contributions, they feel appreciated and inspired to sustain their commitment. Adding more, the result agrees with the view of Harris and Jones (2017) that effective school leaders prioritize teachers' professional growth and provide opportunities for ongoing development. A supportive supervisory environment that encourages continuous learning fosters teachers' dedication to improving their skills and knowledge.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The main goal of this research was to assess the impact of various aspects of school head leadership proficiency on teachers' classroom organization commitment. This was achieved through a non-experimental quantitative study utilizing a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 190 elementary school teachers from Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur, as respondents using a stratified random sampling approach. To ensure the reliability and internal consistency of the survey instrument, the researcher modified and improved existing survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school. The leadership proficiency of school heads in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur got an overall mean of 3.43 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, the leadership proficiency of school heads in terms of curriculum and assessment, teacher development and support, instructional leadership, and resource management obtained mean scores of 3.49, 3.62, 3.30, and 3.32, respectively.

Teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur has an overall mean of 3.34 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, in teachers' classroom organization, commitment in terms of passion for teaching, commitment to student success, personal sacrifice, and innovation and creativity obtained mean scores of 3.30, 3.38, 3.24, and 3.42, respectively. Leadership proficiency of school heads has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .554, p < 0.05$). School heads' Leadership proficiency in curriculum and assessment and teacher development and support significantly influenced the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur, as evidenced by the F-value of 27.837 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.351 indicated that the leadership proficiency of school heads had contributed significantly to the vari-

ability of the teachers' classroom organization commitment by 35.10

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The leadership proficiency of school heads in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur was extensive. This suggests that school administrators exhibit high proficiency across various domains, including curriculum design, assessment practices, instructional leadership, teacher growth, and resource allocation. Their expertise in these areas contributes to educational institutions' overall effectiveness and success, fostering a culture of excellence and continuous improvement. Moreover, instructional leadership is a hallmark of effective school leaders, as they guide and support teachers in implementing best practices and innovative teaching methods. They foster a culture of continuous improvement by modeling effective instructional strategies, providing constructive feedback, and facilitating professional development opportunities for educators. Teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur was moderately extensive. The outcome indicates that teachers effectively execute their duties, deliver a satisfactory educational experience, and sustain stable morale. Nonetheless, they may not exceed expectations or exhibit exceptional zeal or innovation in their teaching methodologies. When teachers fulfill their roles effectively, they ensure that students receive a quality education and feel supported in their academic endeavors. This includes delivering instruction, providing feedback, assessing student progress, and fostering a positive learning environment. The result showed that the leadership proficiency of school heads has a significant positive relationship with the commitment of teachers to classroom organization in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. This implies that effective school administrators establish transparent expectations and objectives for teachers. When educators clearly understand

their responsibilities and specific targets to aim for, they are more inclined to demonstrate dedication toward accomplishing these objectives. School heads' Leadership proficiency in curriculum and assessment; teacher development and support are the domains that significantly influenced the teachers' classroom organization commitment in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. This affirmed that teachers' classroom organization commitment is a function of the leadership proficiency of school heads in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur. When teachers receive meaningful feedback and recognition, it promotes a culture of continuous improvement and professional growth within the school community. Competent school administrators provide constructive feedback and recognition to teachers for their efforts. When educators receive meaningful feedback and acknowledgment for their contributions, they feel valued and motivated to maintain their dedication.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education (DepEd) may develop policies prioritizing leadership training and professional development programs for school administrators, enhancing their skills in providing constructive feedback, fostering a supportive work environment, and recognizing teacher contributions. DepEd may also allocate resources to support ongoing research and evaluation efforts to identify effective leadership practices that positively impact teacher commitment and classroom organization. School heads may engage in continuous professional development to strengthen their leadership skills related to providing meaningful feedback, fostering a positive school culture, and supporting teacher growth and development. They may also foster a collaborative and supportive work environment where teachers feel valued, respected, and empowered to contribute to the school's mission and goals. Teachers may actively seek feedback from school leaders and colleagues to identify areas for improvement and professional growth

and actively engage in reflective practices to enhance teaching effectiveness. They should also advocate for professional growth and development opportunities, such as mentorship programs, peer collaboration, and ongoing training opportunities focused on enhancing classroom organization and instructional effectiveness. Future researchers may collaborate with practitioners and policymakers to translate research findings into actionable recommendations and best practices for enhancing teacher commitment and classroom organization in diverse educational settings. By implementing these recommendations collaboratively, stakeholders can work towards creating school environments that foster teacher commitment and support effective classroom organization, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes.

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